

Towards predictive control of trunk internal loads: modeling musculotendon loads and predicting muscle excitations

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Abstract—Low back pain is prevalent among industrial workers due to heavy lifting and poor posture, causing significant back injuries globally and affecting health and productivity. Existing back-support exoskeletons (BSEs) lack closed-loop control for musculotendon unit (MTU) or joint loads. This study proposes a framework for closed-loop control of L5/S1 joint loads, featuring a simplified BSE dynamics model, a muscle excitation predictor (MEP), and a nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC) algorithm. The simplified model matches the neuromusculoskeletal model with a correlation %0.98, and the MEP has a prediction accuracy of 0.86 ± 0.06 . Future work will develop the MPC algorithm to finalize the control framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

BSEs controllers are classified into active and passive types. However, most research on active controllers focuses on non-predictive types, which fail to anticipate repetitive conditions, while passive controllers struggle with adapting to varying loads. To address this, we propose a framework for future MPC research, shown in Fig. 1. It has two main components (highlighted in blue). The first is a lumped muscle model with actuator for simplifying the trunk muscles, developed from Erector Spinae Muscle (ESM) data using Electromyography (EMG) and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors [1] and optimized by a genetic algorithm (GA), aiming to reduce flexion-extension moments and compression forces. The second component involves developing an MEP predictor using Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NNMF) and regression methods to simulate future muscle excitation within the MPC framework. Finally, we discuss specific design considerations for future MPC controllers.

II. METHODS

A. Modelling the lumped muscle model with BSE

We developed a lumped muscle model to capture the dynamic and kinematic properties of stoop movements.

1) *Model kinematics*: We developed a pulley model (Fig. 2.a) with the MTU to describe human bending dynamics during lifting, where a pulley with a rope (MTU) and a rigid body with a front mass rotate around the L5/S1 center of rotation, yielding lumped MTU length and moment arm [3].

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Fig. 1. Control diagram illustrating the integration of the lumped muscle model, MEP predictor, and MPC.

Fig. 2. (a) Lumped muscle model assisted by BSE. (b), (d), and (f) Comparison of experimental and modeled torques at L5/S1 during stooping with 5 kg, 10 kg, and 15 kg loads. (c), (e), and (g) Comparison of experimental and modeled L5/S1 angles (θ) during stooping with 5 kg, 10 kg, and 15 kg loads.

Simplified model of the exoskeleton-assisted subject, primarily focused on the stoop motions at the L5/S1 joint

$$L^{MT} = \sqrt{L_1^2 - R^2} + R \cdot \Delta\theta \quad (1)$$

where θ represents the angle between the trunk and the ground, which is linearly related to the L5/S1 flexion-extension angle, with θ being ten times the L5/S1 flexion-extension angle. The length from the tangent point of the muscle element and the pulley to the intersection point of the muscle element and the trunk is L^{MT} , and L_1 , L_2 , and R represent the length of the trunk with respect to the L5/S1 joint, the length between the L5/S1 joint to the center of mass, and radius of the pulley (Eq. 1). Specifically, $L^{MT} = L^{MT0} + \Delta L^{MT}$ represents the MTU length, where L^{MT} and L^{MT0} denote the current and original lengths of the MTU, respectively, and ΔL^{MT} is the change in length, illustrating the kinematic properties. The moment arm Ma is equal to the radius R of the disc.

2) *Model dynamics*: The MTU force $F^T(\dot{L}^{MT}, \dot{L}^M, \theta)$ can be derived from the dynamic model [4]

$$I\ddot{\theta} = F^T(\theta, \text{activation}, P) \cdot M_a + T_{ac} - mgL_4 - (M + m_{ac})gL_3 \quad (2)$$

The ODE model is described by the equation above, where I represents the moment of inertia of the upper limb with the load. The torques MgL_3 and mgL_4 correspond to the center of mass and weight of the upper limb, respectively, relative to L5/S1. T_{ac} is the torque assisted by the actuator. For simplification, the weight of the device is neglected ($m_{ac} = 0$). P is the optimization parameter (see Eq. 2).

3) *Experiment*: We used 8 EMG sensors on the muscle groups: iliocostalis, longissimus thoracis, and rectus abdominis, along with 9 IMU sensors on the upper limbs[1]. The subject performed stoop motions with 5, 10, and 15 kg loads, with movement cycles of 3.7, 4.4, 5.3, 6.9, and 9.6 seconds, repeating each condition 3 times, while recording real-time data using the CEINMS toolbox.

4) *Model optimization*: We developed a subject-specific model using the experimental data collected from each subject. The training parameters were $P = (L_1, L_2, R, L_oM_{nominal}, L_{sT}, F_oM)$ and were obtained by fitting our simplified model using GA. $L_oM_{nominal}$, L_{sT} , and F_oM represent optimal muscle fiber length, tendon slack length, and optimal muscle force. The cost function used in this optimization problem is:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^n \|T_{exp} - T_{model}\|_2 + b \sum_{i=1}^n \|\theta_{exp} - \theta_{model}\|_2 \quad (3)$$

The T_{exp} and θ_{exp} were derived using the CEINMS toolbox during stoop movements, integrating EMG signals with IMU sensors and a load of 5, 10, and 15 kg, and b is the weighting factor of kinematic and dynamic optimization in the cost function J (Eq. 3). The model will be verified through CEINMS toolbox during the above conditions at execution time 5.3 seconds Hz with a 2 ms sample time.

B. Developing the MEP predictor

Since any predictive controller requires future muscle excitation inputs as reference, we designed a subject-specific MEP predictor based on the approach outlined in [5].

$$V_{n \times m} = W_{n \times c} \cdot H_{c \times m} \quad (4)$$

First, we apply NMF for dimensionality reduction on the original data, obtaining non-negative factors. The average of these factors for each component provides the mean values, which are then used to train the parameters of the double Gaussian function $XP(t)$, $(A_1, A_2, \mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2)$, forming the matrix W . This results in a parameterized excitation primitives matrix W (Eq. 5).

$$XP(t) = A_1 e^{-\frac{(t-\mu_1)^2}{2\sigma_1^2}} + A_2 e^{-\frac{(t-\mu_2)^2}{2\sigma_2^2}} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. The (a) correlation and (b) RMSE between the MEP profile generated by the MEP predictor and the experimental muscle excitation with movement cycles from 3.7 to 9.6 seconds.

Next, we train the weighting matrix H using data factorized from EMG profiles under 25 stoop conditions, combining cycle times of 3.7, 4.4, 5.3, 6.9, and 9.6 seconds with load weights of 5, 10, and 15 kg, all performed by the same subject. Multiplying the new W and H matrices yields the MEP predictor, evaluated under these conditions as a reference for future controller design.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The back muscle is modeled using a lumped muscle approach, verified with the CEINMS toolbox during a stoop task with the 5-15kg loads at a execution time of 5.3 seconds, integrating EMG signals with IMU sensors. The correlation coefficients between experimental and model data are as follows: for the stoop condition, the lumped muscle model shows a coefficient of 0.98 to 0.99 for torque and 0.27 to 0.35 for θ with loads ranging from 5 to 15 kg (Fig. 2.b-g). (Fig. 3) demonstrates the accuracy of the MEP predictor verifying in the stoop conditions with movement cycles of 3.7, 4.4, 5.3, 6.9, and 9.6 seconds. The results indicate the correlation between the MEP predictor's output and experimental muscle excitation (0.86 ± 0.06), as well as the RMSE (0.10 ± 0.06).

Moreover, future work should focus on the specific design of MPC on a prototype, validate the models with larger datasets, incorporate squat movements to optimize the model, introduce the Extended Kalman Filter to improve measurements, and integrate the system with exoskeleton hardware for practical testing

IV. CONCLUSION

This study developed a simplified back muscle model and MEP predictor for MPC design in stoop conditions, providing a robust framework for real-time exoskeleton control and future design of MPC.

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